
DATA-DRIVEN APPROACHES IN HEALTHCARE: CHALLENGES AND EMERGING TRENDS

Adegoke A. Israel

Federal University of Technology.

Minna

adegoke.m1701038@st.futminna.edu.ng

Lazarus Uduma Igwe

Federal University of

Technology, Minna

Lazarusudumai@gmail.com

Daniel A. Izenyi

Federal University of Technology. Minna.

izenyim1701925@st.futminna.edu.ng

Abstract

In ways never seen before, data is taking over and transforming the all-healthcare sphere. Related to emerging artificial intelligence technologies, they hold the potential to establish the groundwork for a novel medical paradigm that prioritizes the uniqueness of every individual. Encouraging the reader to learn more about data-driven initiatives in the health industry, this paper is structured into four sections. Part one presents three ideologies that, although they overlap in certain areas, offer distinct perspectives on the use of data to ensure that each individual receives a personalized health care. The idea of data-driven design is examined in section two. The growing difficulties in handling vast amounts of data and their effects on people, organizations, and society are linked to innovations in other fields like AI and customized healthcare. The third half of the paper addresses the ethical and legal issues raised by artificial intelligence, a new technology that is starting to disrupt the health sector. In conclusion, section four details how the healthcare sector has developed into a significant testing ground for AI applications, with venture capitalists and entrepreneurs realizing the immense potential this technology can provide.

Data is changing the healthcare industry in particular and the economic landscape in general in ways that are unprecedented. When combined with state-of-the-art technologies such as sophisticated intelligence systems, it has the capacity to create a new medical paradigm that is centered on the individual needs of each patient. However, current healthcare solutions far too frequently result in poor patient outcomes and ineffective decision-making. In order to provide more individualized, efficient, and successful healthcare solutions, we require improved decision-making. How should we walk this path? Is it possible to predict health condition more accurately and to a wider audience at the same time? How can we make these solutions available to the wider public without sacrificing novelty and privacy? In our paper and presentation, we address these issues.

1 Outcome-Centric Care, Patient-focused Care, and the P4 Medicine model: Complementary or Conflicting?

The origins of concepts such as P4 medicine, result-based care, and patient-centered care can be traced back to the close of the 20th century (Gerteis et al. 1993; Hood et al. 2004). The idea that healthcare is changing from reactive disease treatment to person- or patient-centered care was considered speculative more than 20 years ago (Louw et al. 2017). A number of reports by the US Institute of Medicine (National Research Council (US) Committee on a New Biology for the 21st Century: Ensuring the United States Leads the Coming Biology Revolution 2009) or European initiatives like the recently launched Innovative Medicines Initiative project have articulated the fundamentals of these approaches, which are now widely accepted. Result-based care also Valued-based case and patient-centered care are two different but related care philosophies. Patient-centered care prioritizes the patient and their family in all decision-making and quality assessment processes, encompassing several aspects of patient-centeredness. According to research conducted by the Picker Institute, patient-centered care has eight dimensions: (1) respect for the patient's expressed needs, values, and preferences; (2) information and education; (3) care access; (4) emotional support to allay fears and anxieties; (5) family and friend involvement; (6) continuity and secure transition between health care settings; (7) physical comfort; and (8) care coordination. Despite the fact

that these dimensions were first applied to hospital-based care, ambulatory care could also benefit from their application (Gerteis et al. 1993). Value-based care, on the other hand, is characterized as the provision of treatment that is primarily evaluated based on healthcare outcomes, including cost. Patient-centeredness is one significant but not always preeminent quality measure in this definition of value (Tseng and Hicks 2016). By combining the patient-centered and value-based care models, patients should also be given the freedom to gather data about their health outcomes and the access and authority to utilize it for important purposes, such as co-managing their own treatment with their medical professionals. In this perfect world, "computer-based guidance and communications systems" improve the doctor-patient relationship, medical records are accessible online, and patients routinely complete surveys about their experiences, which are then shared with clinicians in "real time" to help them provide better care (Elwyn et al. 2020). A vital element of a healthcare system that guarantees that every patient has access to the type of care that suits them is patient-centered care. In order to guarantee the best results, including quality and satisfaction, this model is crucial for both treating the illness and attending to the social and personal requirements of the patient. A 360-degree view of patient data that is available to the patient and the care team is necessary to treat the whole patient with this degree of customisation. Improved and more intelligent collaboration between healthcare providers is necessary to achieve improved patient outcomes for value-based healthcare. Leroy Hood and other systems medicine pioneers have long promoted the "P4" model of predictive, preventative, personalized, and participatory medicine (Weston and Hood 2004; Hood et al. 2012). Patients, customers, and doctors are now starting to receive tailored information about each person's distinct health experience, including both health and sickness at the molecular, cellular, and organ levels, thanks to systems approaches to biology and medicine. By treating the causes of disease rather than its symptoms and tailoring therapy to each individual's unique biology, this knowledge is reducing the cost of treating illness. Additionally, as customers see the effects of lifestyle choices, it provides the foundation for them to take tangible action to improve their health.

While utilizing technology and our growing understanding of environment-biology interactions, evidence-based therapies, and the underlying processes of chronic

diseases, P4 medicine has the potential to significantly lessen the burden of chronic diseases (Sagner et al. 2017). According to P4 medicine, each patient's involvement is essential to implementing the other three P4 components. Effective self-management requires active patient involvement, which includes sharing decisions about their clinical or therapeutical approach with patients and implementing their participation in disease management through the use of innovative technologies to achieve meaningful and applicable improvements in outcomes (Baiardini and Heffler 2019). In order to create a completely individualized care plan for each patient, evidence-based prediction and preventive care integrates genetic and social determinants of health with the practice of medicine based on the most recent research. It surpasses the belief that just five percent of the sickest patients should undergo genomic testing, an idea that originated from the days when genetic testing was extremely expensive. Precision health genetic testing now only costs a few hundred dollars, and that number is going down. This upfront expense is more than justified by the potential savings in the long run. The application of preventative genetics at the community level is essential to understanding an individual's poly-genomic elevated risk for disease or physical characteristic, as well as which treatments they cannot metabolize, do not respond to well, or have adverse effects from. Pharmacogenomics research is currently a key component of personalized and preventative medicine being used in clinical settings.

The Food and Drug Administration (FDA) of the United States has identified more than 120 pharmacogenomics associations, and the list is still expanding, for which available data suggests a modification in drug management or a possible influence on safety (Kim et al. 2021). With funding from the European Commission's Horizon-2020 initiative, the Ubiquitous Pharmacogenomics (U-PGx) Consortium sought to assess the overall therapeutic utility of integrating a panel of pharmacogenomics indicators into standard care (van der Wouden et al. 2017). The scientific guidelines on pharmacogenomics provided by the European pharmaceuticals Agency assist medicine makers in preparing applications for marketing authorization of human pharmaceuticals.

Health systems in Europe do not commonly monitor long-term health outcomes, despite patients' great desire in doing so. Examples of such outcomes include symptom severity or functional status over time. Thus, one neglected tactic for

encouraging the shift to a new paradigm in the healthcare system is patient engagement in gathering and applying pertinent health outcomes data and information (Nguyen et al., 2021). In addition, information incorporating patient viewpoints have to be accessible and taken into account when making choices about health policy. Value-based models are becoming increasingly popular among stakeholders, although they are still understudied and not widely used (Porter et al. 2016). There are a number of conflicts that make it difficult to align the objectives and focus of value-based care, patient-centered care, and P4 medicine ideologies. These conflicts include a lack of patient experience, a vague definition of preferred measures, and payer-focused rather than patient-focused conceptions of cost (Tseng and Hicks 2016). But putting these three ideologies' areas of convergence into practice offers real chances to change the paradigm of the healthcare system as it currently exists. This is crucial in a world where chronic diseases, such as cancer and cardiovascular disease, are becoming more common, as are co-morbidities related to them, and late-life disabilities. A sizeable amount of the worldwide gross domestic product (GDP) is spent on health care expenses. According to estimates from the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD), the average GDP share of nations that make up the OECD was 8.8% in 2018. This percentage has been relatively constant since 2013. (OECD 2019). With health spending amounting to 16.9% of GDP, the United States leads the world in this regard. Switzerland comes in second with 12.2%. Following the US and Switzerland, a number of affluent nations—including Sweden, Germany, France, and Japan—all allocate nearly 11% of their GDP to healthcare. Additionally, it's estimated that these nations waste up to 20% of their health care budgets.

In order to achieve a rational distribution of limited resources, there is growing evidence and recognition that healthcare finance should be centered on outcomes rather than on paying for the services rendered. The transition from volume to value necessitates the design, development, and implementation of integrated solutions, services, and products that add value by effectively and efficiently enhancing patient outcomes. The implementation of this transition requires access to copious amounts of data and a multitude of findings regarding the effects of clinical interventions. More effort and dedication from patients and all others involved in

the health field are still required, even with the many projects that are now in progress to acquire these data (Porter and Lee 2013).

2 Data-Centric Healthcare

In 2006, data science entrepreneur and British mathematician Clive Humby declared, "Data is the new oil." Unrefined, though, makes it incredibly useless. Data must be reliable, accurate, complete, accessible, shareable, and—most importantly—used in order to create value. Similar to numerous other sectors, the healthcare industry consistently produces enormous volumes of data from a wide range of sources, including biochemical examinations, electronic health records, vital signs, patient-reported outcomes, clinical trials, insurance claims, administrative data, and, more recently, omics (genomics, transcriptomics, proteomics, metabolomics, radiomics, microbiomics). These datasets collectively constitute large data sets that are essential for improving patient care quality, lowering readmission rates, assisting in decision-making, and achieving overall gains in results. But large data gathering and data-driven healthcare are not the same thing (SanchezPinto et al. 2018; Savadjiev et al. 2020). While the amount of data available is increasing and has the potential to spark a new wave of fact-based innovation in the healthcare industry, automation is necessary to improve operational agility and clinical outcomes by streamlining procedures and making decisions more clear. Healthcare organizations need to transition from gathering healthcare data to being data-driven healthcare organizations as the regulatory landscape increasingly favors patient-centered and value-based treatment. To enable team members to make the best decisions possible and the company to achieve its objectives, becoming a data-driven healthcare institution necessitates more investment and resources (Carra et al. 2020). In order to reduce future individual risks of disease and negative health impacts and to advance patient-centered and value-based care models, new data-driven health management should be applied in clinical decision-making (Grossglauser and Saner 2014; Kriegova et al. 2021). Determining a data infrastructure, data-driven procedures, a data-centric culture, and a cybersecurity framework are required to reach this new status. Four main pillars make up data-driven healthcare: (1) patient,

healthcare provider, and organizational use of data; (2) data regulation to guarantee privacy, security, and accountability; (3) technologies and computational techniques that support healthcare providers in making data-driven decisions to enhance patient outcomes; and (4) data regulation the innovations that are driven by data and that are driving the production of new data. A data-driven healthcare plan should aim to achieve the following objectives in order to enhance the utilization of data by all parties involved, including patients, healthcare providers, and organizations: (1) encouraging education and literacy to increase patients' and healthcare professionals' understanding of the importance of data-driven healthcare; (2) developing an integrated healthcare system with a patient-centered focus by making data easily and widely accessible; and (3) encouraging management initiatives and investing in data governance to lessen resistance to change within healthcare organizations. Organizational culture is currently the largest barrier to data-driven healthcare, outpacing technological or financial issues. In order to guarantee the safe interchange of patient information, safeguard the integrity of medical records and applications, and manage access to healthcare systems and apps that contain personal data, data accountability, privacy, and security are complicated subjects. It's critical to monitor and evaluate regulatory compliance for data processing at the corporate and individual levels. The formulation of data management rules, training for personnel handling health data, and assistance with the deployment of "secure by design" information systems are all essential components of a data-driven healthcare strategy. Furthermore, the shift to data-driven healthcare involves monitoring and accountability from all parties involved, including the government, patients, healthcare providers, insurance companies, and suppliers of healthcare providers. It also affects how data is collected, processed, analyzed, and used.

Patients and healthcare providers can already collaborate more successfully to enhance patient outcomes thanks to existing technologies. Health technology is starting to become a commodity, as evidenced by the rise of wearable medical devices, cloud-based applications and storage that enable better communication and an improved patient experience, and the use of medical mobile devices for remote monitoring.

Innovative computational techniques that were created to carry out intelligent monitoring, create predictive models for early disease detection, prevention, diagnosis, treatment, and prognosis, as well as to analyze or suggest treatment and intervention plans, underpin all of these technologies (Wong-Lin et al. 2020). Although computational techniques can extract value from large amounts of data, they frequently encounter significant obstacles such as the volume and relevance of the input data, the readability and accessibility of the data, and the lack of interoperability of the data. The acquired data needs to be clean, comprehensive, accurate, and consistent for usage across systems in order to be considered actionable. In order to ensure peer review, it should also be easily legible and accessible to a variety of stakeholders with varying functions, such as the scientific community, regulatory bodies, and healthcare professionals (Heijlen and Cromptvoets 2021). The use of artificial intelligence for the development of precise, preventive, and personalized medicine—which combines big data analytics and statistical techniques, or machine learning algorithms—is one of the future innovations that depends on these continuing trends (Handelman et al. 2018; Abul-Husn and Kenny 2019; Loncar-Turukalo et al. 2019; Morganti et al. 2019; Goecks et al. 2020).

3 Standards and Legal Issues Posed by Artificial Intelligence

Ever since its inception at the Dartmouth Summer Research Project on Artificial Intelligence in 1956, artificial intelligence (AI) has failed to live up to the expectations of many. AI is rapidly moving from theory to reality thanks to recent developments in machine learning techniques, the availability of huge data, and the presence of supercomputing infrastructures. Artificial intelligence is boosting the deployment of deep data application services as a big data engine (Jiang et al., 2021). The latest advancements in AI can be largely attributed to deep learning. Deep learning techniques have significantly outperformed conventional machine learning techniques in a number of prediction problems. This new approach, however, does a relatively poor job of describing its reasoning procedures and outcomes. Explainability and transparency are very important in many real-world applications, like medical diagnosis, for the users who are impacted by AI decisions.

(Xu and colleagues, 2019). The last ten years have seen a gradual integration of AI, driven by deep learning, into routine medical practice. Significant advancements have been made in medical diagnosis (Dias and Torkamani 2019; Kehl et al. 2021), medical image processing (Ahmad et al. 2019; Ardila et al. 2019; McKinney et al. 2020), medical process optimization (Bellini et al. 2019; Gutierrez 2020), medical education (van der Niet and Bleakley 2021), and other applications (Oliveira 2019). However, the absence of established procedures and moral and legal oversight continues to hinder widespread deployments in clinical practice. The primary difficulties surrounding the application of AI in healthcare are related to the nature of technology itself, the intricacies of providing legal support in terms of efficiency and safety, privacy, ethics, and liability issues. Although the application of AI in clinical settings has the potential to significantly improve patient care, it also presents several ethical issues, including informed permission to use, safety and transparency, and data protection (Gerke et al. 2020). The idea behind informed consent, according to Wikipedia, is that patients should receive enough information to make an informed decision about their medical care before acting on that knowledge on their own. A healthcare provider is frequently held accountable for guaranteeing that the consent a patient provides is informed. Informed consent might cover disclosure of personal information, medical interventions, and research projects involving the patient. Although the application of AI in clinical settings has the potential to significantly improve patient care, it also presents several ethical issues, including informed permission to use, safety and transparency, and data protection (Gerke et al. 2020). The idea behind informed consent, according to Wikipedia, is that patients should receive enough information to make an informed decision about their medical care before acting on that knowledge on their own. A healthcare provider is frequently held accountable for guaranteeing that the consent a patient provides is informed. Informed consent might cover disclosure of personal information, medical interventions, and research projects involving the patient. (Tauginiene et al. 2021). These inquiries are particularly pertinent when the AI uses "black-box" algorithms, which can be the consequence of noninterpretable machine-learning strategies that are exceedingly challenging for medical practitioners to fully comprehend (Xu et al. 2019). Informed consent is converted into a user agreement in the context of AI

health apps that are either linked to wearable sensors or not. The question of how this user agreement relates to informed consent remains unanswered. This topic is especially important because most user agreements are consented to without a face-to-face conversation. Furthermore, the majority of consumers frequently disregard user agreements, fail to comprehend the terms of service, and are ignorant of the intricacies involved in updating hardware or software. These inquiries are particularly pertinent when the AI uses "black-box" algorithms, which can be the consequence of non-interpretable machine-learning strategies that are exceedingly challenging for medical practitioners to fully comprehend (Xu et al. 2019). Informed consent is converted into a user agreement in the context of AI health apps that are either linked to wearable sensors or not. The question of how this user agreement relates to informed consent remains unanswered. This topic is especially important because most user agreements are consented to without a face-to-face conversation. Furthermore, the majority of consumers frequently disregard user agreements, fail to comprehend the terms of service, and are ignorant of the intricacies involved in updating hardware or software. For instance, using Framingham Heart Study data to estimate the risk of cardiovascular events in non-White populations has produced biased findings, including risk estimates that are both too high and too low. According to Gijsberts et al. (2015), the majority of research on primary prevention and cardiovascular disease risk scores, such as the groundbreaking Framingham Risk Score and the European SCORE, has been conducted on a predominantly White population to date. If there have been few (or no) genetic research in a given community, then any algorithm created to forecast outcomes from genetic discoveries will be biased. The development of AI algorithms should prioritize transparency. Patients and healthcare providers should be aware of the kind of data that are used and whether the system contains any biases. Even while it is conceivable to imagine an open-data model that can be verified by anybody in a hypothetical setting, this kind of implementation is really subject to a number of restrictions. An open-data strategy must protect patient anonymity and may give rise to concerns about intellectual property and investment. AI systems should be utilized proactively to improve health equity rather than just guarding against the flaws that have already been discovered. The models' conception, execution, and assessment must take distributive fairness into account

in order for this fact to hold true (Murdoch 2021). Notwithstanding present obstacles, artificial intelligence (AI) has enormous potential to revolutionize the delivery of healthcare services in environments with limited resources since these systems may substitute human experts when they are not easily accessible, which is frequently the situation in underdeveloped areas. As data owners, patients have the right to know how and to what extent their personal health data are recorded and used. The General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) has been in effect in all EU Member States since 2018 and has brought in a new era of data protection law in the EU. Since personal medical information is one of the most private and legally protected types of data, there are serious concerns about how access, control, and use by for-profit parties might change over time with a self-improving AI (Jaremko et al. 2019). Canada's regulations acknowledge that consumers own their private health data and that healthcare professionals are the "information custodians" of such data. The concept of "guardianship" acknowledges the existence of legally protected interests in patient medical records (Powles and Hodson 2017). Currently, a substantial amount of AI technology is controlled by big tech companies like Google, Apple, Microsoft, and others. These businesses are all "preparing, in their own ways, bids on the future of health and on various aspects of the global healthcare industry" (Price and Cohen 2019). The concentration of technological innovation and knowledge in these large tech companies creates a power imbalance where public health institutions may become less able to maintain a balanced partnership in new developments and implementations, even though some data privacy breaches have happened in spite of existing laws, regulations, and privacy policies. AI presents a new difficulty in accessing vast volumes of patient data, on top of the potential for power abuses related to data governance. In this case, the ownership and placement of the data servers that house patient information are crucial considerations. With very few exceptions, the rule now mandates that patient data remain in the jurisdiction from which it was obtained. Public trust concerns are understandable given the current environment, which has already seen multiple instances of huge corporations abusing patient health data without the consent of the individuals involved. Patients, the general public, and even public health institutions may become less trusting of one another, which may lead to increased public scrutiny or even legal action against commercial applications of AI in

healthcare. Numerous studies demonstrate that health-related data far surpassed what the original privacy protection regulations were intended to safeguard. The US Congress approved the Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act (HIPAA) Privacy Rule in 1996; however, since it only covers specific health information generated by "covered entities" or their "business associates," it has significant gaps when it comes to the current healthcare environment. The 2018 Centers for Disease Control and Prevention. Thankfully, a plethora of new rules have been proposed to control AI data protection, responsibility assessment, and supervision. The European Commission released a white paper on AI in February 2020. "It is vital that European AI is based on our fundamental values and rights, such as human dignity and the protection of privacy," the Commission emphasized in the white paper, highlighting the "European Approach" to AI. (2020 European Commission). The "Artificial Intelligence Act," a proposed AI regulation, was unveiled in April 2021 (European Commission 2021). The majority of medical AI applications fall under the category of "high risk" applications, which will be governed by this regulation. The main requirements for European Medical AI are non-discrimination, explainability, privacy by design, and human oversight. Human evaluation is necessary before any action is done based on medical AI conclusions, as mandated by EU basic rights (also see Art. 14 of the proposed AI Act). Put differently, European Medical AI is legally dependent on having a human involved. More importantly, the patient's free and informed consent is needed. This suggests that the patient and doctor should make joint decisions, with the patient having the last word. The employment of explainable AI in medicine is essentially mandated under the European fundamental rights, as this argument concerning informed patient decisions makes clear. The main requirements for European Medical AI are non-discrimination, explainability, privacy by design, and human oversight. Human evaluation is necessary before any action is done based on medical AI conclusions, as mandated by EU basic rights (also see Art. 14 of the proposed AI Act). Put differently, European Medical AI is legally dependent on having a human involved. More importantly, the patient's free and informed consent is needed. This suggests that the patient and doctor should make joint decisions, with the patient having the last word. The employment of explainable AI in medicine is essentially mandated under the European fundamental rights, as this argument concerning informed

patient decisions makes clear. The current framework for fundamental rights is extensive, but it does not address every legal issue that arises with the application of AI in medicine. Regrettably, there is a significant exception that involves liability law concerns, which are especially troubling for the community creating AI-based solutions. When medical AI does injury, who will be held legally accountable? Who should I contact: the hospital, the healthcare professional, the manufacturer, the maintenance personnel, the IT supplier, or the software developer? The Commission declared that it would soon offer more clarification in this area and suggest a rigorous liability strategy together with an obligatory AI damage insurance program. The legal criteria for the use of medical AI are already more obvious than they were a few years ago, despite the remaining unanswered concerns. This is crucial to note because the community creating AI-based products does not seem to take this into consideration.

4 Financial Pull-in Trends in Healthcare Artificial Intelligence Sector

In the past five years, the healthcare sector has emerged as a major testing ground for artificial intelligence (AI) applications. This is due to the realization by venture capital (VC) investors and startups alike of the immense potential that AI solutions can offer in terms of speeding up the recruitment process for clinical trials and vaccine development, identifying potentially fatal adverse drug events, enhancing patient care, cutting down on hospital wait times and staffing requirements, and lowering healthcare costs. When they became aware of the necessity of investing in AI for healthcare, investors all over the world shifted their portfolios in this direction. Healthcare AI value is predicted to increase at a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 46.2% from USD 6.9 billion in 2021 to USD 67.4 billion by 2027 (Markets and Markets 2020). Healthcare AI funding has increased at an unprecedented rate because to the surge in demand. After 111 agreements in the first quarter of 2021, healthcare AI businesses have raised a record \$2.5 billion in cash. Compared to the \$1 billion raised in Q1 2020, this amounts to a 140% increase (CBInsights 2021b; Fierce Healthcare 2021). AI is here to stay, as seen by the investments made in and the current applications for this technology.

Capital investments in the health sector are necessary to address the various challenges that European health policies face, including the aging of the population and the decline in public health spending. In order for nations to be well-prepared for unanticipated catastrophes like the Covid-19 pandemic, investments in the health sector must be promoted, but social protection and the promotion of healthy lifestyles must also be prioritized. To act as a spur for the expansion of the health sector, incentive policy models must be developed immediately. The expansion of the health sector boosts the overall economy, thus European governments stand to gain from social returns on venture capital investments in healthcare as well as the promotion of healthy lives. Since investing in a population's overall well-being promotes economic growth, it is important to continuously enhance health care with a strong emphasis on disease prevention. The COVID-19 epidemic has brought about an unprecedented catastrophe for the healthcare sector, as it has for other industries. The digital health space, which includes virtual health care with a particular emphasis on mental health and well-being, has accelerated due to this problem. As COVID-19 vaccinations become more widely available, attention is turning to the pandemic's long-term impacts, which include developments in a number of health-related fields, such as telemedicine, artificial intelligence in healthcare, medical devices, mental health, women's health, omics, and cyber security (CBInsights 2021a). Investments in artificial intelligence (AI) for healthcare in 2022 are probably going to be mostly focused on increasing backend efficiency, including processing claims with AI or utilizing robotic process automation (RPA) to support treatment. When AI and RPA are combined, intelligent automation is produced, frequently with the help of bots, to closely resemble human interaction. It's most likely that short-term investments in AI will go toward creating second views, diagnostic assistance tools, and routine error detection rather than toward autonomously diagnosing patients.

The biggest obstacle to AI adoption in this day and age, when its use in healthcare facilities and society at large is expanding, is not whether the technology will be capable enough to be helpful, but rather making sure it is appropriately integrated into routine clinical practice. When preparing to work with clients in the healthcare arena or starting their own healthcare AI adventures, corporates and organizations should keep in mind five topics in the translation to clinical practice (IT Pro Portal

2021). These five topics are: (1) which AI technology is more suitable for the intended use; (2) who is using AI applications primarily; (3) which software (commercial or open-source) should be used to build AI solutions; (4) whether to build or purchase software; and (5) how to ensure compliance with AI standards and regulations. Real technical experts emphasize that their companies already use data integration, including data science platforms, data annotation, business intelligence (BI), and natural language processing (NLP). It's evident now that the most forward-thinking healthcare companies value their data highly, utilizing electronic health records and technologies like natural language processing (NLP) to integrate data from disparate silos and obtain a comprehensive understanding of their organizational processes and patients' clinical progress. Physicians and patients are increasingly the top users of AI applications in the user space. Physicians and patients are increasingly using AI apps instead of data scientists and tech staff. AI will only advance when chatbots and other interactive and automation technologies get more sophisticated. Since technology offers a level of accessibility and convenience that makes many jobs easier, like making appointments, obtaining clinical information, and even managing remote health care, this growth is already having a significant impact on the delivery of patient care. Physicians and patients are increasingly the top users of AI applications in the user space. Physicians and patients are increasingly using AI apps instead of data scientists and tech staff. AI will only advance when chatbots and other interactive and automation technologies get more sophisticated. Since technology offers a level of accessibility and convenience that makes many jobs easier, like making appointments, obtaining clinical information, and even managing remote health care, this growth is already having a significant impact on the delivery of patient care. Mature businesses typically opt out of third-party evaluation or software vendor representation in favor of using their own data and monitoring systems. However, businesses who are just beginning to investigate AI are more receptive to utilizing software suppliers' solutions. For those with the resources to continue their AI efforts internally, using models customized to each company's unique needs while retaining data inside the company is a wise choice. AI-powered solutions will be essential to operations and safety in highly regulated industries like pharmaceuticals and healthcare. Organizations must therefore set up a compliance management program to handle

pertinent requirements from applicable AI authoritative norms in order to scale the deployment and use of AI. The European Union's legal framework on artificial intelligence (AI) is combined with a new plan that is in coordination with the member states to ensure the safety and fundamental rights of individuals and companies, all the while promoting AI acceptance, investment, and innovation. AI has the potential to drastically alter the healthcare and life sciences sectors in ways that were unthinkable just a few years ago, given its current state of development.

REFERENCES

- Abul-Husn NS, Kenny EE (2019) Personalized medicine and the power of electronic health records. *Cell* 177:58–69
- Ahmad OF, Soares AS, Mazomenos E, Brandao P, Vega R, Seward E, Stoyanov D, Chand M, Lovat LB (2019) Artificial intelligence and computer-aided diagnosis in colonoscopy: current evidence and future directions. *Lancet Gastroenterol Hepatol* 4:71–80
- Ardila D, Kiraly AP, Bharadwaj S, Choi B, Reicher JJ, Peng L, Tse D, Etemadi M, Ye W, Corrado G, Naidich DP, Shetty S (2019) End-to-end lung cancer screening with three-dimensional deep learning on low-dose chest computed tomography. *Nat Med* 25:954–961
- Baiardini I, Heffler E (2019) Chapter 21 - The patient-centered decision system as per the 4Ps of precision medicine. In: Agache I, Hellings P (eds) *Implementing precision medicine in best practices of chronic airway diseases*. Academic Press, London, pp 147–151
- Bellini V, Guzzon M, Bigliardi B, Mordonini M, Filippelli S, Bignami E (2019) Artificial intelligence: a new tool in operating room management. Role of machine learning models in operating room optimization. *J Med Syst* 44:20
- Carra G, Salluh JIF, Ramos FJDS, Meyfroidt G (2020) Data-driven ICU management: using big data and algorithms to improve outcomes. *J Crit Care* 60:300–304
- CBInsights (2021a) Here are the most active healthcare investors. <https://www.cbinsights.com/research/most-active-healthcare-vcs/>. Accessed 8 Jan 2022
- CBInsights (2021b) State of healthcare Q1'21 report: investment & sector trends to watch. <https://www.cbinsights.com/research/report/healthcare-trends-q1-2021/>. Accessed 8 Jan 2022
- Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (2018) Health insurance portability and accountability act of 1996 (HIPAA). <https://www.cdc.gov/phlp/publications/topic/hipaa.html>. Accessed 17 Dec 2021

- Dankar FK, Gergely M, Malin B, Badji R, Dankar SK, Shuaib K (2020) Dynamic-informed consent: a potential solution for ethical dilemmas in population sequencing initiatives. *Comput Struct Biotechnol J* 18:913–921
- Dias R, Torkamani A (2019) Artificial intelligence in clinical and genomic diagnostics. *Genome Med* 11:70
- Elwyn G, Nelson E, Hager A, Price A (2020) Coproduction: when users define quality. *BMJ Qual Saf* 29:711–716
- European Commission (2020) WHITE PAPER on artificial intelligence—a European approach to excellence and trust. https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/default/files/commission-white-paperartificial-intelligence-feb2020_en.pdf. Accessed 16 Nov 2021
- European Commission (2021) Proposal for a regulation of the European parliament and of the council. Laying down harmonised rules on artificial intelligence (Artificial intelligence act) and amending certain union legislative acts. <https://bit.ly/3AcDsCa>. Accessed 16 Nov 2021
- Fierce Healthcare (2021) Global investment in telehealth, artificial intelligence hits a new high in Q1 2021. <https://bit.ly/3qtk4hQ>. Accessed 12 Nov 2021
- Gerke S, Minssen T, Cohen G (2020) Ethical and legal challenges of artificial intelligence-driven healthcare. *Artif Intell Healthc*:295–336. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B1978-1010-1012-818438818437.800012-818435>
- Gerteis M, Edgman-Levitan S, Daley J, Delbanco TL (1993) *Through the patient's eyes: understanding and promoting patient-centered care*. Jossey-Bass, San Francisco, CA
- Gijsberts CM, Groenewegen KA, Hofer IE, Eijkemans MJC, Asselbergs FW, Anderson TJ, Britton AR, Dekker JM, Engström G, Evans GW, de Graaf J, Grobbee DE, Hedblad B, Holewijn S, Ikeda A, Kitagawa K, Kitamura A, de Kleijn DPV, Lonn EM, Lorenz MW, Mathiesen EB, Nijpels G, Okazaki S, O'Leary DH, Pasterkamp G, Peters SAE, Polak JF, Price JF, Robertson C, Rembold CM, Rosvall M, Rundek T, Salonen JT, Sitzer M, Stehouwer CDA, Bots ML, den Ruijter HM (2015) Race/Ethnic differences in the associations of the

Framingham risk factors with carotid IMT and cardiovascular events. *PLoS One* 10:e0132321 Goecks J, Jalili V, Heiser LM, Gray JW (2020) How machine learning will transform biomedicine. *Cell* 181:92–101

Grossglauser M, Saner H (2014) Data-driven healthcare: from patterns to actions. *Eur J Prev Cardiol* 21:14–17

Gutierrez G (2020) Artificial intelligence in the intensive care unit. *Crit Care* 24:101

Handelman GS, Kok HK, Chandra RV, Razavi AH, Lee MJ, Asadi H (2018) eDoctor: machine learning and the future of medicine. *J Int Med* 284:603–619

Heijlen R, Crompvoets J (2021) Open health data: mapping the ecosystem. *Digit Health* 7:20552076211050167

Hood L, Heath JR, Phelps ME, Lin B (2004) Systems biology and new technologies enable predictive and preventative medicine. *Science* 306:640–643

Hood L, Balling R, Auffray C (2012) Revolutionizing medicine in the twenty-first century through systems approaches. *Biotechnol J* 7:992–1001

IT Pro Portal (2021) The state of AI in healthcare: five key findings enterprises should know. <https://www.itproportal.com/features/the-state-of-ai-in-healthcare-five-key-findingsenterprises-should-know/>. Accessed 15 Oct 2021

Jaremko JL, Azar M, Bromwich R, Lum A, Alicia Cheong LH, Gibert M, Laviolette F, Gray B, Reinhold C, Cicero M, Chong J, Shaw J, Rybicki FJ, Hurrell C, Lee E, Tang A (2019) Canadian association of radiologists white paper on ethical and legal issues related to artificial intelligence in radiology. *Can Assoc Radiol J* 70:107–118

Jiang L, Wu Z, Xu X, Zhan Y, Jin X, Wang L, Qiu Y (2021) Opportunities and challenges of artificial intelligence in the medical field: current application, emerging problems, and problemsolving strategies. *J Int Med Res* 49:3000605211000157

Kehl KL, Xu W, Gusev A, Bakouny Z, Choueiri TK, Riaz IB, Elmarakeby H, Van Allen EM, Schrag D (2021) Artificial intelligence-aided clinical annotation of a large multi-cancer genomic dataset. *Nat Commun* 12:7304

Kim JA, Ceccarelli R, Lu CY (2021) Pharmacogenomic biomarkers in US FDA-approved drug labels (2000–2020). *J Pers Med* 11:179

- Kriegova E, Kudelka M, Radvansky M, Gallo J (2021) A theoretical model of health management using data-driven decision-making: the future of precision medicine and health. *J Transl Med* 19:68–68
- Loncar-Turukalo T, Zdravevski E, Machado da Silva J, Chouvarda I, Trajkovic V (2019) Literature on wearable technology for connected health: scoping review of research trends, advances, and barriers. *J Med Internet Res* 21:e14017
- Louw JM, Marcus TS, Hugo JFM (2017) Patient- or person-centred practice in medicine? - A review of concepts. *Afr J Prim Health Care Fam Med* 9:e1–e7
- Markets and Markets (2020) Artificial Intelligence in Healthcare Market by offering (Hardware, software, services), technology (Machine learning, NLP, context-aware computing, computer vision), application, end user and geography - global forecast to 2027. <https://bit.ly/3GBUm07>. Accessed 17 Dec 2021
- McKinney SM, Sieniek M, Godbole V, Godwin J, Antropova N, Ashrafian H, Back T, Chesus M, Corrado GS, Darzi A, Etemadi M, Garcia-Vicente F, Gilbert FJ, Halling-Brown M, Hassabis D, Jansen S, Karthikesalingam A, Kelly CJ, King D, Ledsam JR, Melnick D, Mostofi H, Peng L, Reicher JJ, Romera-Paredes B, Sidebottom R, Suleyman M, Tse D, Young KC, De Fauw J, Shetty S (2020) International evaluation of an AI system for breast cancer screening. *Nature* 577:89–94
- Morganti S, Tarantino P, Ferraro E, D'Amico P, Duso BA, Curigliano G (2019) Next generation sequencing (NGS): a revolutionary technology in pharmacogenomics and personalized medicine in cancer. *Adv Exp Med Biol* 1168:9–30
- Murdoch B (2021) Privacy and artificial intelligence: challenges for protecting health information in a new era. *BMC Med Ethics* 22:122
- National Research Council (US) Committee on a New Biology for the 21st Century: Ensuring the United States Leads the Coming Biology Revolution (2009) A new biology for the 21st century: ensuring the united states leads the coming biology revolution. National Academies Press, Washington, DC
- Nguyen H, Butow P, Dhillon H, Sundaresan P (2021) A review of the barriers to using PatientReported Outcomes (PROs) and Patient-Reported Outcome Measures (PROMs) in routine cancer care. *J Med Radiat Sci* 68:186–195

- OECD (2019) Health working papers. OECD health working paper no. 110. Health spending projections to 2030. <https://bit.ly/3tLxAQ3>. Accessed 22 Nov 2021.
- Oliveira AL (2019) Biotechnology, big data and artificial intelligence. *Biotechnol J* 14:1800613
- Porter ME, Lee TH (2013) The strategy that will fix health care. *Harv Bus Rev* 91:50–70
- Porter ME, Larsson S, Lee TH (2016) Standardizing patient outcomes measurement. *N Engl J Med* 374:504–506
- Powles J, Hodson H (2017) Google DeepMind and healthcare in an age of algorithms. *Health Technol (Berl)* 7:351–367
- Price WN, Cohen IG (2019) Privacy in the age of medical big data. *Nat Med* 25:37–43
- Rajkomar A, Hardt M, Howell MD, Corrado G, Chin MH (2018) Ensuring fairness in machine learning to advance health equity. *Ann Int Med* 169:866–872
- Sagner M, McNeil A, Puska P, Auffray C, Price ND, Hood L, Lavie CJ, Han ZG, Chen Z, Brahmachari SK, McEwen BS, Soares MB, Balling R, Epel E, Arena R (2017) The P4 health spectrum – a predictive, preventive, personalized and participatory continuum for promoting healthspan. *Prog Prev Med* 2:e0002
- Sanchez-Pinto LN, Luo Y, Churpek MM (2018) Big data and data science in critical care. *Chest* 154:1239–1248
- Savadjiev P, Reinhold C, Martin D, Forghani R (2020) Knowledge based versus data based: a historical perspective on a continuum of methodologies for medical image analysis. *Neuroimaging Clin N Am* 30:401–415
- Tauginiene L, Hummer P, Albert A, Cigarini A, Vohland K (2021) Ethical challenges and dynamic informed consent. In: Vohland K, Land-Zandstra A, Ceccaroni L, Lemmens R, Perelló J, Ponti M, Samson R, Wagenknecht K (eds) *The science of citizen science*. Springer International Publishing, Cham, pp 397–416
- Tseng EK, Hicks LK (2016) Value based care and patient-centered care: divergent or complementary? *Curr Hematol Malig Rep* 11:303–310
- U.S. Food and Drug Administration (2021) FDA releases artificial intelligence/machine learning action plan. <https://www.fda.gov/news->

[events/press-announcements/fda-releases-artificialintelligencemachine-learning-action-plan](#). Accessed 8 Oct 2021

- van der Niet AG, Bleakley A (2021) Where medical education meets artificial intelligence: ‘Does technology care?’ *Med Educ* 55:30–36.
- van der Wouden CH, Cambon-Thomsen A, Cecchin E, Cheung KC, Dávila-Fajardo CL, Deneer VH, Dolžan V, Ingelman-Sundberg M, Jönsson S, Karlsson MO, Kriek M, Mitropoulou C, Patrinos GP, Pirmohamed M, Samwald M, Schaeffeler E, Schwab M, Steinberger D, Stingl J, Sunder-Plassmann G, Toffoli G, Turner RM, van Rhenen MH, Swen JJ, Guchelaar HJ (2017) CORRIGENDUM: implementing pharmacogenomics in Europe: design and implementation strategy of the ubiquitous pharmacogenomics consortium. *Clin Pharmacol Ther* 102:152
- Weston AD, Hood L (2004) Systems biology, proteomics, and the future of health care: toward predictive, preventative, and personalized medicine. *J Proteome Res* 3:179–196
- Wong-Lin K, McClean PL, McCombe N, Kaur D, Sanchez-Bornot JM, Gillespie P, Todd S, Finn DP, Joshi A, Kane J, McGuinness B (2020) Shaping a data-driven era in dementia care pathway through computational neurology approaches. *BMC Med* 18:398–398
- Xu F, Uszkoreit H, Du Y, Fan W, Zhao D, Zhu J (2019) Explainable AI: a brief survey on history, research areas, approaches and challenges. In: Tang J, Kan MY, Zhao D, Li S, Zan H (eds) *Natural language processing and Chinese computing NLPCC 2019 Lecture notes in computer science*. Springer International Publishing, Cham, pp 563–574.